

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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ENHANCING SELF-CARE OF NURSES: A HEALTHY NURSE HEALTHY
NATION™ PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to enhance self-care (which has been operationalized as physical activity) among Healthy Nurse Health Nation (HNHN™) participants. Specific aims are to describe nursing factors associated with light to moderate physical activity, vigorous physical activity, and muscle strengthening exercises. A secondary aim is to develop online educational materials and activities to encourage physical activity for use by the HNHN™ Initiative.

Nurses are the largest workforce in healthcare and are trained to care for a variety of patient types; however, that training may not include self-care principles. Both extrinsic factors (such as lack of support from institutions) as well as intrinsic factors (such as personal beliefs and personal attributes) may influence self-care behaviors of nurses. The literature suggests that a lack of self-care behaviors can lead to negative outcomes such as moral distress, burnout, job dissatisfaction, anger, stress, and depression.

Tenets of Social Cognitive Theory guided the development and implementation of this DNP project. Secondary data from a large online survey employed by HNHN™ (N=15,492 nurses) were analyzed with appropriate descriptive (e.g., numbers and percentages) and inferential statistics (e.g., correlations, p-values) to identify facilitators and barriers to physical activity in nurses. A gap analysis was completed in order to

identify necessary educational materials and activities to contribute to the HNHNTM initiative.

Nurses within the 41-50 age group as well as nurses who identified as Black/African American were least likely to engage in physical activity. Poor physical/mental health and pain were shown to be the strongest barriers to physical activity ($r = -.143$, $r = -.117$, $p < 0.001$ respectively), while receiving emotional support and wellness training were shown to be the strongest facilitators ($r = .134$, $r = .097$, $p < 0.001$ respectively). The development of online self-care videos and a physical activity social media challenge are planned. The number of hits on the self-care video and physical activity challenge will provide evidence of the efficacy of the project interventions.

Nurse self-care is a topic of increasing interest among healthcare professionals. To improve self-care behaviors, research recommends assessing healthcare workers' self-efficacy in addition to providing continuous individualized educational and motivational training programs. When looking at self-care domains such as physical activity, nurses were found to be unhealthier than the average American. Contributing to the HNHNTM initiative by assessing needs, relaying vital information, and creating periodic challenges can aid in engaging a diverse population of nurses while providing motivation to initiate and sustain health-promoting behaviors

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BACKGROUND

Research suggests that high-stress, demanding work environments may contribute to poorer health outcomes (Williams, Costley, Bellury, & Moobed, 2018). In addition, some work settings exhibit a culture of shame, bullying, and indifference to collegial relationships (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2017; Mills, Wand, & Fraser, 2015). In particular, caring for the sick or dying often leads to nurses' dealing with exhaustion, emotional strain, and compassion fatigue (Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017; Williams et al., 2018). As a result, nurses experience higher rates of obesity, smoking, insomnia, and stress as compared to the average American (ANA, 2017).

The overall poor health of nurses could be the result of several factors. First, many nurses experience high levels of stress related to the nature and location of their work. Nurses may also experience stress due to the multitude of roles they perform in their personal and professional lives (Mills et al., 2015). Most nurses are female and may be caregivers both in their profession and in their personal lives. These varying roles may interfere with the practice of health-promoting behaviors. Nurses may see competing demands that interfere with behaviors that support a healthy lifestyle (Petiprin, 2016). While informal caregiving is reported to provide significant meaning and purpose for many individuals, it can also serve as additional substantial stress for the individual serving as the caregiver (Richard & Shea, 2011).

One way that nurses can mitigate the influence of stress on their health is to engage in self-care behaviors. Self-care is defined as activities individuals participate in to achieve an ideal health status and support health-promoting behaviors (Richard & Shea, 2011). Health-promoting behaviors and activities are major components of self-

care (Richard & Shea, 2011) and include actions like maintaining healthy relationships, eating healthy, staying physically active and managing stress (Ross, Bevans, Brooks, Gibbons, & Wallen, 2017). Self-care also incorporates integrative practices such as stress-relieving massages, guided imagery, relaxation, and art activities (Lamke, Catlin, & Mason-Chadd, 2014). These activities are influenced by individual demographics, relationships, and behavioral factors (Khodaveisi, Omid, Farokhi, & Soltanian, 2017).

Lack of self-care practices among healthcare workers has negative effects such as burnout, anger, depression, stress, and dissatisfaction (Lamke, et al., 2014; Williams et al., 2018). In contrast, the advantages of a healthcare workforce focused on self-care are higher quality of care, improved patient outcomes, and increased job satisfaction (Alexander, Rollins, Walker, Wong, & Pennings, 2015; ANA, 2017; Williams et al., 2018). Leaders benefit from making self-care a priority for workers and ensuring programs and policies within their organizations to address the growing concern of the health status of nurses and the effects these issues may have on patient outcomes (Williams et al., 2018). Work environments also play an important role in helping nurses, as well as other healthcare workers, believe that they can continuously practice health-promoting behaviors on and off the job (McCormick & Hayes, 2017).

Problem Statement

Nurses are the largest workforce in healthcare (Alexander et al., 2015) and are trained to care for a variety of patient types; however, that training does not usually include self-care (Mills et al., 2015). Although there is evidence detailing the importance of improving self-care, there are barriers that prevent healthcare workers from participating in these activities. To address these barriers, the ANA developed Healthy

Nurse Healthy Nation (HNHN)™ as an initiative to challenge registered nurses nationwide to improve America's health by focusing on self-care (ANA, 2017). The main areas targeted as part of the initiative are safety, rest, physical activity, nutrition, and quality of life (ANA, 2017).

As healthcare workers, many nurses make less than healthy lifestyle choices to deal with the emotional and physical demands of the profession (ANA, 2017; Ross et al., 2017). Both extrinsic factors, such as lack of support from institutions, as well as intrinsic factors, such as personal beliefs, influence nurses' self-care decisions (Ross et al., 2017). The American Holistic Nurses Association reviewed data from HNHN™ survey responses and identified physical activity as the practice of self-care in which nurses need most improvement.

Purpose Statement

Therefore, the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to address barriers to initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors specific to physical activity as identified by HNHN™. The aims of the project were twofold: to describe personal and environmental factors experienced by nurses that may inhibit or enhance self-care behaviors and to develop educational materials and activities focused on increasing physical activity sustainability to contribute to the HNHN™ initiative.

Supporting Framework

Models and theories are widely used as support for organizing and developing innovative projects (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). A methodology that provides a foundation for the implementation, data collection, and analysis of these projects can assist in identifying a population's issues and needs (Van Gelderen, Krumwiede, Krumwiede, &

Fenske, 2018). Bandura's social cognitive theory (SCT) has been used in the development of health promotion programs, and its constructs influence the propensity to initiate or sustain healthy behaviors (Richard & Shea, 2011). This theory guided the analysis of literature and survey data to identify healthcare workers' personal and environmental factors in terms of their efforts to practice self-care.

Bandura describes SCT as a triangular relationship among personal, behavioral, and environmental circumstances (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Personal factors can include individual characteristics, past experiences, knowledge of self-care, and perceived abilities to practice self-care (Richard & Shea, 2011; Williams et al., 2018). Environmental circumstances may be described as relationships, support systems, work setting, work load, and home environment (Williams et al., 2018). The SCT triangular relationship shows that both personal and environmental factors can enhance or inhibit self-care behaviors (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). For the purpose of this project, self-care behaviors were described as physical activities individuals participate in to reach an ideal health status.

SCT has been used within the field of education and disputes prior views of learners as passive reactors to their environment (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). According to Bandura, individuals can view others' behaviors as well as their outcomes and use those discoveries to improve their own behaviors (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). SCT focuses on five major theoretical components: modeling, outcome expectations, self-efficacy, goal setting, and self-regulation (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). These components include perceptual factors like benefits and self-efficacy, which determine whether individuals participate in health-promoting behaviors (Khodaveisi et al., 2017).

The modeling components of SCT focuses on the precept that individuals learn by emulating the behaviors of others (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Modeling further includes four processes: attention, retention, production, and motivation. These processes are listed as steps that detail how people first focus on a behavior, then retain the observed behavior for access in the future when they determine if they are motivated to repeat the action (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Outcome expectations applies to results that people expect to get from their actions (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). This thought process can influence whether individuals decide to continue or stop a behavior.

Self-efficacy is described as perceived ability to perform a particular action (Richard & Shea, 2011). According to Costlow and Bornstein (2018), self-efficacy is often based on four factors: mastery experience (increase in self-efficacy after experiencing positive outcomes), vicarious experience (increase in self-efficacy when an individual with similar characteristics experiences success), social persuasions (external reassurance or discouragement), and somatic-emotional states (self-efficacy determined by physical and emotional wellness). Self-efficacy may influence outcome expectations because those with higher levels of confidence in their abilities expect more positive outcomes. Goal setting, another component of SCT, involves individuals' deciding on anticipated behavioral outcomes (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Goal setting can be affected by both outcome expectations and self-efficacy, since individuals usually base their goals on the results they expect as well as what they believe they can achieve.

The last major component of SCT is self-regulation and applies to the capability to improve and maintain behaviors (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Self-regulation further breaks down into three sub-processes: self-observation, self-judgment, and self-reaction.

According to Bandura, individuals first observe their own behaviors, then evaluate their behaviors through self-judgment to take action in changing their behaviors through self-regulation (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). All essential elements of SCT may lead to understanding of self-care agency and determining what makes individuals capable or incapable of performing self-care activities (Richard & Shea, 2011). The major components of SCT can be depicted within the triangular relationship among personal, behavioral and environmental factors that contribute to favorable behaviors (see Figure 1).

Data Analysis Utilizing SCT

This DNP project aimed to describe barriers to self-care practices specific to physical activity as well as revise and develop educational content and activities to improve nurse activity levels. Data from an ongoing survey conducted by the ANA on self-care and physical activity were analyzed by applying SCT regarding the effects of personal and environmental factors on self-care behaviors. Personal factors were evaluated by identifying demographics and experiences of survey participants. Personal factors also included self-efficacy and self-regulation. Self-efficacy was analyzed by determining factors that may interfere with nurses' beliefs that they can participate in physical activity as well as activities that may enhance their perceived abilities to engage in this self-care. Self-regulation was examined by identifying survey data that described how nurses evaluated their current behaviors and their ability to maintain health-promoting behaviors. Environmental factors were evaluated by examining survey data concerning support systems, work culture, and workload. Self-care behaviors related to

physical activity were examined by identifying how often survey participants engage in these activities and their ability to sustain them.

Figure 1. Modified social cognitive theory.

Note. Based on information from Costlow and Bornstein (2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This DNP project sought to identify barriers to self-care by analyzing data collected by the American Nurses Association (ANA) as well as peer-reviewed studies. Results will be used to develop evidence-based educational content and activities to contribute to the HNHNTM initiative sponsored by the ANA. This literature review highlights the positive effects of self-care behaviors, challenges faced by individuals in practicing self-care, and methods that increase health-promoting behaviors. Literature regarding the importance of nurses' self-care is growing as more individuals become aware of health concerns (Mills et al., 2015).

A search for peer-reviewed literature was conducted by using the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature, ScienceDirect, PubMed, Ovid Nursing, Wiley Online Library, Directory of Open Access Journals, and Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. Key search terms were nurse self-care, nurse health promotion, nurse health behavior, and health-promoting behaviors of nurses. Studies regarding self-care and health promotion were also expanded to include medical doctors and physical therapists as study subjects or participants. Other search terms were nurse burnout, nurse occupational health, nurse self-care decisions, nurse self-compassion, and occupational health coaching to find articles that listed barriers to self-care as well as methods that enhance self-care.

The search was limited to articles published between January 2014 and January 2020 with the exception of one article published in 2011 that contained fundamental information regarding self-care (Richard & Shea, 2011). Other search limitations were peer-reviewed articles and journals written in English. Journal articles that identified

patients, student nurses, or any other non-healthcare workers as the sole subjects of self-care were excluded from the review except for two randomized-controlled trials that were included because of their higher level of evidence regarding methods to enhance self-care. One systematic review, three randomized control trials, two non-randomized trials, eight correlational/observational studies, one qualitative study, and six literature reviews were identified for this literature review. Articles chosen were divided into four major themes: (a) effects of self-care behaviors, (b) personal factors that influence self-care, (c) environmental factors that influence self-care, and (d) methods to enhance self-care. For this project, self-care included all health-promoting behaviors that may contribute to physical activity.

Effects of Self-Care Behaviors

Managing stress, enhancing relationships with others, and practicing self-care were mentioned in the ANA's (2017) Scope and Standards of Practice as responsibilities of registered nurses (Lamke et al., 2014). Nonetheless, self-care is a term that many nurses are aware of but do not fully understand (Cranick, Miller, Allen, Ewell, & Whittington, 2015). The World Health Organization defines self-care as the activities individuals and communities participate in to improve health and avoid illness (Cranick, et al., 2015). Physical activity is a significant aspect of self-care and involves practices such as walking, aerobic exercise, and muscle strengthening (ANA, 2017; Ross et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2018). Terms like "resiliency," "mindfulness," and "wellness," are often used to describe the effects of physical activity and other self-care benefits (Alexander et al., 2015; Halm, 2017; Lamke et al., 2014). Generally, self-care involves participating in health-promoting behaviors on a daily basis. Self-care behaviors like

physical activity enhance resiliency and wellness and decrease nurse stress and burnout (Alexander et al., 2015; Lamke et al., 2014; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017).

Mental, physical, emotional, and spiritual outcomes that increase nurse well-being are highly associated with practicing self-care. With emotional resilience, healthcare workers are better equipped to handle stressful work situations, which leads to increased job satisfaction and optimal patient outcomes (Alexander et al., 2015; Cranick et al., 2015). Studies by Alexander et al. (2015) and Lamke et al. (2014) show that self-care practices significantly decreased nurses' mental and emotional issues such as emotional exhaustion, anxiety, and stress. Although these studies could benefit from longitudinal examinations of these practices, short-term effects are also important to note.

Personal Factors Associated with Self-Care

Some may suggest that the nature of nursing creates personal barriers that prevent self-care practices. In fact, the literature suggests that nurse attributes such as demographics, experiences, knowledge, and self-efficacy influence the propensity for initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors. The act of caring for others who have extreme needs can lead to emotional exhaustion and compassion fatigue, which may hinder the ability to focus on caring for oneself (Williams et al., 2018; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017). In addition, nurses usually have multiple caregiver roles, both at home and work, which can contribute to burnout and exhaustion (Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017). Many nurses experience a multiplicity of professional and personal roles that compete for time and attention. Clearly, nurses, by virtue of their roles, need strategies to manage stress, stay healthy, and complete all obligations concurrently (Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei, 2018).

A study on nurse entrepreneurs conducted by Vannucci and Weinstein (2017) found that juggling multiple roles and time management were listed as the greatest challenges to self-care. Some studies suggest that younger nurses who lacked work experience were less likely to engage in self-care (Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei, 2018; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017; Williams et al., 2018). In contrast, one study found that increased age was associated with fewer health-promoting behaviors (Kurnat-Thoma, El-Banna, Oakcrum, & Tyroler, 2017). Younger nurses with less work experience may not have had as much time to develop a sense of purpose with their job, which can lead to job dissatisfaction, stress, anxiety, and lack of motivation to focus on their health (Ross et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2018).

Self-efficacy, defined herein as a belief in one's ability to practice self-care (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018), is noted to be a significant determinant of whether an individual initiates or sustains self-care behaviors (Khodaveisi et al., 2017; Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei, 2018; Richard & Shea, 2011; Ross et al., 2017). The gap between knowledge of self-care activities and the actual practice of these behaviors becomes more apparent when nurses have little or no belief that they can successfully engage in self-care behaviors (Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei, 2018; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017). Vannucci and Weinstein (2017) found that lack of motivation has a negative influence on health-promoting behaviors and could explain why one study showed no increase in self-care behaviors even when nurses were employed by organizations that offered wellness programs (Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2017). Nurses who do not feel empowered or motivated to participate in health-promoting behaviors often experience adverse health outcomes (Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017).

Environmental Factors Associated with Self-Care

Healthcare environments have a significant effect on self-care behaviors. The literature suggests that occupational health resources be provided to nurses within their work setting to encourage or support self-care behaviors (Alexander et al., 2015; Lan, Subramanian, Rahmat, & Kar, 2014; Ruotsalainen, Verbeek, Marine, & Serra, 2015). Work environments that promote healthy behaviors among nurses decrease burnout and contribute to resiliency (Halm, 2017; Lan et al., 2014). The majority of studies reviewed suggest that healthcare work environments, many of which are stressful and demanding, benefit from their staff incorporating self-care behaviors (Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2017; Lamke et al., 2014; Williams et al., 2018). Ruotsalainen et al. (2015) highlighted these benefits of stress relief in their systematic review on reducing occupational stress of healthcare workers. Based on the findings of the studies reviewed, administrators should consider developing programs to support employee self-care to improve work environments.

The literature supports that environmental factors identified by the SCT framework may serve as barriers to self-care. Environmental factors include support systems, work culture, and work load (Figure 1). Although the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention developed an initiative to promote health in the workplace, nurses remain the unhealthiest group in the healthcare workforce (Williams et al., 2018). Over half of nurses in the United States report themselves to be overweight and experience high levels of stress (ANA, 2017; Williams et al., 2018). Work environments may lack resources or support for their staff, which can foster negative interpersonal experiences between healthcare workers (Ross et al., 2017; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017).

Interpersonal conflicts between nursing staff and other healthcare workers and lack of perceived support from management can contribute to a culture of discouragement (Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei; Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017).

Nurses often work 12-hour shifts and tend to bypass necessary breaks due to excessive workload (Williams et al., 2018). Shift work and the various complicated tasks that are required of nurses have been linked to lack of sleep, which can lead to fatigue and a perceived inability to participate in healthy behaviors (Najaf-Abadi & Rezaei, 2018; Richard & Shea, 2011; Ross et al., 2017). Although nurse-to-patient ratios are now taken into consideration to enhance nurse and patient safety, nursing professionals often deal with impractical workloads and insufficient staffing to assist with work demands (Vannucci & Weinstein, 2017). These factors can be considered environmental stressors and contribute to unhealthy behaviors like overeating, poor diet, and lack of sleep (Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2017). Coping mechanisms from interventions that can enhance self-care are needed to help replace these behaviors with those that can lead to healthier outcomes (Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2018).

Methods to Enhance Self-Care

The literature provides several recommendations that may help healthcare workers initiate and sustain self-care behaviors. Increased self-efficacy enhances one's perceived ability to engage in self-care activities (Richard & Shea, 2011). Increased knowledge of strategies to overcome barriers as well as gaining experiences in work and personal life, are factors that can increase self-efficacy (Khodaveisi et al., 2017; Richard & Shea, 2011). Gaining experiences in life can help individuals to gain confidence and comfort in their overall abilities, which enhances self-efficacy (Costlow & Bornstein,

2018). Educational programs that focus on learning strategies to practice health-promoting behaviors daily as well as continuously training individuals on these strategies have been suggested as methods to increase self-efficacy and enhance self-care (Blum, 2014; Khodaveisi et al., 2017; Richard & Shea, 2011). However, before participating in educational programs, health risk behaviors and perceived ability to change those behaviors must be assessed to select training activities that can promote change for each individual (Kouwenhoven-Pasmooij et al., 2018; Mills et al., 2015).

Nurses may not be aware of their self-efficacy levels regarding healthy behaviors or their ability to manage their emotions and stress. Assessments targeted toward these elements can help nurses to develop awareness of their own emotional intelligence and abilities that may motivate them towards taking charge of their own health (McCormick & Hayes, 2017; Mills et al., 2015; Richard & Shea, 2011). Self-care interventions tailored to the individual through an assessment of their current behaviors and which guide them to make better choices may be an effective approach to improving self-care (Kouwenhoven-Pasmooij et al., 2018).

Health coaching has been studied as a method to increase self-efficacy as well as self-regulation (West-Leuer, 2014). Self-regulation involves monitoring one's own behaviors, analyzing these behaviors, and having the ability to change or sustain them to reach desired outcomes (Costlow & Bornstein, 2018). Self-regulation could be addressed with the help of nurse leaders by taking initiative to analyze the self-care practices of their employees as well as implementing activities to help them sustain healthy behaviors (Ross et al., 2018). Several studies highlight methods to increase self-care and demonstrate the importance of adequate and continuous training for healthcare workers to

self-regulate their stress and emotions, which can ultimately increase healthy behaviors (Cho, Han, & Park, 2018; Kouwenhoven-Pasmooij et al., 2018; Ross et al., 2018; West-Leuer, 2014; Willgens & Hummel, 2016).

Although nurses have in-depth knowledge of healthy behaviors and provide this education to patients, that knowledge does not necessarily translate to self-action (Cho et al., 2018; West-Leuer, 2014). This suggests that an intervention is required to help motivate nurses to continue practicing self-care. Healthcare leaders are advised to initiate health-promoting programs, like coaching, that can provide this motivation through continuous goal setting and constructive feedback (Ross et al., 2018; West-Leuer, 2014; Willgens & Hummel, 2016).

Conclusion

Nurse self-care is a topic of increasing interest among healthcare professionals. The literature showed personal factors such as young age, multiple caregiver roles, time constraints, and lack of self-efficacy were barriers to self-care. Environmental factors like shift work, increased workload, and lack of support from organizations also inhibit self-care practices. To improve self-care behaviors, research recommends assessing healthcare workers' self-efficacy in addition to providing continuous individualized educational and motivational training programs. When looking at self-care domains such as physical activity, nurses were found to be unhealthier than the average American (ANA, 2017). Contributing to the ANA's HNHN™ initiative by further analyzing self-care survey data can aid in identifying personal and environmental factors that may inhibit or enhance self-care behaviors. By comparing survey data to information found in the literature, the author can develop educational content and activities that will benefit

nurses and their objectives for sustaining health-promoting behaviors specific to physical activity.

METHODS

The purpose of this doctoral project was to identify barriers associated with initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors specific to physical activity as identified by Healthy Nurse Healthy Nation (HNHN)TM. This section describes the ethical considerations for the project, the design used by the author, the project's setting, and sample population. Measures used to evaluate self-care behaviors specific to physical activity, project procedures, as well as the analysis and evaluation plan are also outlined within this section. A description of the analysis plan for survey data from the HNHNTM website is provided. Educational materials from the American Holistic Nurses Association (AHNA) are reviewed. A gap analysis plan to identify targets to improve Continuing Nurse Education (CNE) content for nurses is also detailed. The design, implementation, and evaluation of CNE content were based on American Nurse Credentialing Center (ANCC) guidelines (American Holistic Nurses Association [AHNA], 2018a).

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from California State University, Long Beach (CSULB) was waived. Because an analysis of non-identifiable information was completed, this project was considered exempt by the CSULB IRB.

Design

This evidence-based practice project integrated evidence from the literature review, HNHNTM survey data analysis, and the author's clinical experience to identify challenges nurses face in initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors specific to physical activity. The goal was to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice by revising and

developing self-care support literature and educational activities for the HNHN™ initiative. To meet this aim, the author analyzed a de-identified data set generated from a national survey employed by the American Nurses Association (ANA). The analysis assisted the author in developing educational content and activities geared towards increasing nurse self-care practices specific to physical activity. Educational activity guidelines listed by the AHNA were followed to ensure all content and activities that were developed meet goals for effective practice changes.

Setting

This evidence-based project was conducted as part of the AHNA's contribution to the HNHN™ initiative. The AHNA is a national, professional nursing organization that focuses on building partnerships with patients and communities to incorporate the concept of wholeness into various healing processes. AHNA headquarters is located in Topeka, Kansas. The AHNA offers CNE activities through their bimonthly published magazine, webinars, the *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, and through AHNA annual and regional conferences.

The AHNA is a partner of the HNHN™ initiative, which was created by the ANA as a national challenge to help nurses focus on self-care. HNHN™ offers a website where nurses as well as other healthcare workers can create a personal profile, take an extensive self-care survey, and access resources regarding health-promoting behaviors. The self-care survey is conducted nationally off the website and includes multiple locations.

Sample

The sample population for this project included nurses (N=15,492) who completed the HNHNTM online survey starting February 2, 2017 to May 8, 2019. Members of the AHNA include Registered Nurses (RNs), Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs), Educators, Researchers, Clinical and Operational Managers, Wellness Coaches, Spiritual Counselors, & Business Owners. Within the survey, types of healthcare workers were condensed to Advanced Practice Registered Nurses (APRNs), RNs, and LVNs.

Measures

The Health Risk Appraisal (HRA) is the online survey that was developed by the ANA and Pfizer, Inc, a pharmaceutical company dedicated to public health initiatives. This tool was developed by utilizing a literature review, expert consultations, as well as research group engagement to identify necessary items to include as part of the survey (ANA, 2017). The entire survey contains 94 items and is separated into 3 categories that include: (a) demographics, (b) healthy work environment, and (c) health, safety, and wellness. The HRA was officially made live in October 2013 and had over 14,000 respondents by the time it closed in December 2016 for ANA's *Executive Summary* (ANA, 2017). The HRA is now utilized as a free online survey that nurses can take once they create a profile on the HNHNTM website (www.healthynursehealthynation.org). The survey highlights participants' current self-care behaviors, which include rest, activity, nutrition, quality of life, and safety, and any risks or barriers regarding these target areas. Items within this survey that exhibit nurses failing to practice self-care behaviors specific to physical activity described the extent of the issue. Items that detail processes or behaviors that can enhance physical activity described how the issue can be resolved.

For this project, 4 demographic, 10 multiple-choice, 1 close-ended, and 5 Likert scale items were examined related to physical activity and their determinants. Item responses ranged from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree.” Examples include, “I have access to employer-based exercise facilities and programs” and “In my current work environment, I often have to arrive early or stay late to get my work done.” Other items include, “On average, how many times per week do you do vigorous aerobic workouts (where conversation may be difficult because of large increase in breathing and heart rate)? 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 ,6,” and “How often do you get the emotional support you need? 1) Always, 2) Usually, 3) Sometimes, 4) Rarely, 5) Never,” and “During the past two years, I have received training in wellness (stress management, mindfulness meditation, resiliency, or self-care training) provided by my current employer: 1) Yes, 2) No.”

Analysis Plan for HNHNTM Data

The ANA sent the author a de-identified dataset of the respondents who completed the HRA survey on the HNHNTM website from February 2, 2017 to May 8, 2019. The author collaborated with a statistician to develop an analytic plan to empirically identify challenges that prevent nurses from practicing self-care behaviors specific to physical activity. Baseline characteristics of survey participants including demographics and nurse position were described with measures of central tendency. Associations between independent and dependent variables were analyzed with the appropriate bivariate tests. The statistician selected the Statistical Package Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software to analyze data based on familiarity and expertise. Both measures and data were assessed for clinical validity and relevance to the project purpose. Concurrent with the secondary data analysis, a gap analysis was conducted to

identify gaps in professional practice that can prevent nurses from initiating and sustaining self-care behaviors specific to physical activity.

Procedures Related to Educational Aim

Creation of educational materials was based on the AHNA Individual Educational Activity guidelines for designing CNE content (AHNA, 2018a). The author identified: (a) current CNE content and activities regarding self-care practices specific to physical activity that are available to nurses via the AHNA website, (b) significant CNE content and activities that should be available to nurses to assist them in continuing to participate in physical activity, (c) a description of the gap in knowledge, skills, and/or professional practice related to physical activity, (d) evidence-based validation of the practice gap utilizing the literature review, secondary data analysis, as well as clinical experience, (e) the target audience for the CNE content and activities, and (f) observable and measurable learning outcomes that can contribute to closing the practice gap (see Appendix A). The gap analysis will be utilized to revise AHNA existing CNE content regarding self-care practices specific to physical activity and design new educational content and activities to contribute to the HNHN™ initiative.

Evaluation Plan for CNE Materials

CNE content and activities developed by the author will be evaluated by the AHNA based on the educational design process described within the Individual Educational Activity guidelines for designing CNE content (AHNA, 2018a). The evaluation processes addresses 5 key criteria: (a) adequate completion of the gap analysis, (b) content development and delivery, (c) learner engagement strategies, (d) holistic philosophy, and (e) evaluation of the learning outcomes (see Appendix B).

Learning outcomes will be evaluated for appropriateness to fulfill professional practice gaps.

RESULTS

This DNP project aimed to identify barriers to nurse physical activity for self-care purposes by analyzing data from the national Health Risk Appraisal (HRA) survey conducted by the American Nurses Association (ANA). Results identified the number of survey participants, their demographics, as well as their physical activity level at the time of the survey. Correlations between demographics, survey items, and physical activity levels are also presented within this section utilizing tables.

Survey Sample

Data recorded from nurses who completed the HRA survey on the Health Nurse Healthy Nation (HNHN)TM website between February 2, 2017 to May 8, 2019 were included in the analysis. Fifteen thousand four hundred and ninety-two nurses total completed the survey. Eleven percent ($n=1709$) were Advanced Practice Registered Nurses [APRNs]. Eighty-seven percent ($n=13,488$) were Registered Nurses [RNs], and 2% ($n=295$) were Licensed Vocational Nurses [LVNs]. The ethnic background and age groups of survey participants providing complete data are described in Table 1.

Majority of the survey participants were female (95%) and white/Caucasian ($n=12,070$ [82%]). There was little diversity with 7% ($n=975$) Black/African American, 5% ($n=785$) Asian, and 4% ($n=610$) Hispanic/Latino participants. The remainder of participants either provided multiple/mixed ethnicity selections, stated that they did not know, or declined to state their ethnic background ($n=311$ [2%]). Age groups were more evenly distributed with 26% ($n=3743$) of participants in the 51-60 age range and 11% ($n=1641$) in the 19-30 age range.

Table 1

Sample Characteristics

	Total (n=14759)	APRN (n=1639)	RN (n=12847)	LVN (n=273)
Gender				
Female	n=14041 (95%)	n=1582 (97%)	n=12209 (95%)	n=250 (92%)
Male	n=718 (5%)	n=57 (3%)	n=638 (5%)	n=23 (8%)
Ethnic Background				
	Total (n=14751)	APRN (n=1635)	RN (n=12,846)	LVN (n=270)
White/Caucasian	n=12070 (82%)	n=1422 (87%)	n=10451 (81%)	n=197 (73%)
Black/African American	n=975 (7%)	n=110 (7%)	n=826 (6%)	n=39 (14%)
Asian	n=785 (5%)	n=37 (3%)	n=738 (6%)	n=10 (4%)
Hispanic/Latino	n=610 (4%)	n=38 (3%)	n=559 (4%)	n=13 (5%)
Other/No Response	n=311 (2%)	n=28 (2%)	n=272 (2%)	n=11 (4%)
Age				
	Total (n=14622)	APRN (n=1613)	RN (n=12,741)	LVN (n=268)
19-30	n=1641 (11%)	n=25 (2%)	n=1550 (12%)	n=66 (25%)
31-40	n=3393 (23%)	n=250 (15%)	n=3072 (24%)	n=71 (26%)
41-50	n=3557 (24%)	n=349 (22%)	n=3143 (25%)	n=65 (24%)
51-60	n=3743 (26%)	n=532 (33%)	n=3168 (25%)	n=43 (16%)
61 or older	n=2288 (16%)	n=457 (28%)	n=1808 (14%)	n=23 (9%)

Physical Activity Levels of Survey Participants

APRNs showed higher levels of workouts (exercise) per week than RNs and LVNs (light to moderate workouts per week: mean 2.80 [APRNs] vs. mean 2.48 [RNs] and mean 2.08 [LVNs]; see Table 2). Nurses engaged in less vigorous exercise and muscle strengthening exercise than light to moderate exercise (see Table 2). Majority nurses spent 31-60 minutes on light to moderate exercise and 0-15 minutes in vigorous exercise (see Figure 2).

Table 2

Nurse Position vs. Physical Activity

	Light to Moderate Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Vigorous Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Muscle Strengthening per Week (Mean, SD)
Position			
APRN (n=1709)	(2.80, 2.146)	(1.36, 1.734)	(1.38, 1.76)
RN (n=13488)	(2.48, 2.039)	(1.26, 1.595)	(1.31, 1.67)
LVN (n=295)	(2.08, 2.008)	(1.20, 1.843)	(1.29, 2.106)

*Range: 0-15

Figure 2. Time spent on light to moderate and vigorous workouts: Amount of nurses

Activity levels varied by age. Nurses aged 61 or older showed the highest number of workouts for light to moderate exercises while the 41-50 age group showed the least (mean 2.91 [age 61 or older] vs. mean 2.24 [age 41-50]; see Table 3). Nurses aged 19-30 showed higher numbers of vigorous and muscle strengthening workouts than middle aged nurses (muscle strengthening exercises: mean 1.70 [age 19-30] vs. mean 1.20 [age 41-50] and 1.33 [age 51-60]; see Table 3).

Nurses who identified as White/Caucasian were more likely to engage in light-moderate workouts per week than those who identified as Black/African American, Asian, or Hispanic/Latino (mean 2.59 [White/Caucasian] vs. mean 1.97 [Black/African American], mean 2.04 [Asian], and mean 2.26 [Hispanic/Latino]; see Table 4). Nurses who identified as Hispanic/Latino were more likely to engage in vigorous and muscle strengthening exercises than those who identified as White/Caucasian, Black/African American, and Asian (vigorous workouts per week: mean 1.41 [Hispanic/Latino] vs. mean 1.27 [White/Caucasian], mean 1.08 [Black/African American], and mean 1.21 [Asian]; see Table 4). Black/African American nurses were least likely to engage in light-moderate, vigorous, and muscle strengthening exercises.

Table 3

Age Association with Physical Activity

Age	Light to Moderate Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Vigorous Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Muscle Strengthening Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)
19-30	(2.55, 1.928)	(1.68, 1.656)	(1.70, 1.796)
31-40	(2.40, 1.948)	(1.38, 1.594)	(1.38, 1.670)
41-50	(2.24, 1.890)	(1.23, 1.585)	(1.20, 1.594)
51-60	(2.57, 2.122)	(1.15, 1.632)	(1.22, 1.672)
61 or older	(2.91, 2.320)	(1.02, 1.544)	(1.27, 1.672)

*Range: 0-15

Table 4

Ethnic/Racial Background Association with Physical Activity

Ethnic Background	Light to Moderate Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Vigorous Workouts per Week (Mean, SD)	Muscle Strengthening per Week (Mean, SD)
White/Caucasian	(2.59, 2.082)	(1.27, 1.626)	(1.32, 1.683)
Black/African American	(1.97, 1.830)	(1.08, 1.444)	(1.12, 1.621)
Asian	(2.04, 1.858)	(1.21, 1.472)	(1.33, 1.684)

Hispanic/Latino	(2.26, 1.892)	(1.41, 1.598)	(1.38, 1.741)
Other/No Response	(2.60, 1.998)	(1.68, 2.057)	(1.65, 1.798)

*Range: 0-15

Survey Items and Effects on Physical Activity

Access to employer-based exercise facilities showed a strong correlation to increasing vigorous workouts per week ($r=.075, p<.001$). Access to worksite wellness programs showed a strong correlation to increase in light-moderate workouts per week ($r=.086, p<.001$). Receiving wellness training also showed a strong correlation to increased light-moderate workouts ($r=.097, p<.001$). Arriving early and staying late at work showed a strong correlation to decreasing muscle strengthening exercises ($r= -.072, p<.001$). Poor physical/mental health as well as pain showed the highest correlations to decreasing physical activity overall (light-moderate exercises: $r= -.143$ [poor physical/mental health], $r= -.117$ [pain]; see Table 5). Receiving emotional support showed the highest correlation to increasing physical activity overall ($r=.134$ [light-moderate exercises], $r=.096$ [vigorous exercises], $r=.106$ [muscle strengthening]; see Table 5). Experiencing workplace stress showed a strong correlation to decreasing light-moderate ($r= -.094, p<.001$) and muscle strengthening exercises per week ($r= -.070, p<.001$).

Table 5

Survey Items Correlation to Physical Activity

Survey Item	Light to Moderate Workouts per Week	Vigorous Workout per Week	Muscle Strengthening Workouts per Week
Work the night shift	$r= -.042^*$	$r= .009$	$r=.012$
Access to employer-based exercise facilities	$r=.051^*$	$r= .075^*$	$r=.053^*$

Access to worksite wellness programs	$r=.086^*$	$r=.069^*$	$r=.057^*$
Received wellness training in the past 2 years	$r=.097^*$	$r=.058^*$	$r=.054^*$
Often arrive early or stay late at work	$r= -.062^*$	$r= -.066^*$	$r= -.072^*$
Mental/physical health interfered with physical activity	$r= -.143$	$r= -.113^*$	$r= -.093^*$
Pain interfered with physical activity	$r= -.117^*$	$r= -.119^*$	$r= -.076^*$
Received emotional support	$r= .134^*$	$r=.096^*$	$r=.106^*$
≥ 7 hours of sleep per day	$r= .057^*$	$r=.016^*$	$r=.002^*$
Experience workplace stress	$r= -.094^*$	$r= -.054^*$	$r= -.070^*$
Experience verbal/nonverbal aggression at work	$r= -.040^*$	$r= -.015^*$	$r= -.029^*$

* $p<.001$

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to identify factors associated with initiating and sustaining nurse self-care behaviors specific to physical activity that were identified by the Healthy Nurse Healthy Nation (HNHN)TM Initiative. The findings suggest that physical activity (a self-care behavior) was significantly associated with personal factors (e.g., age, nurse role, ethnicity) as well as environmental factors (e.g., existence of employer support, workplace culture). This project may be the first to identify these factors in such a large sample of nurses from across the nation. Moreover, the results can serve as a foundation for the future development of educational materials to increase physical activity and other self-care modalities. The discussion section examines the results from the Health Risk Appraisal (HRA) analysis within the context of the current literature as well as clinical experiences from the author.

Physical activity is a significant aspect of self-care that should be incorporated into nurse daily life in order to prevent chronic conditions like obesity and heart disease (Ross et al., 2017; Waldrop, 2016). The United States Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) (2019) recommends at least 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate to vigorous physical activity per week as well as muscle strengthening activities at least 2 times per week for adults to maintain optimal health. Current research suggests that registered nurses (RNs) have not been able to meet these guidelines on a regular basis due to lack of motivation and fatigue from stressful work environments (Alexander et al., 2015; Bakhshi, Sun, Murrells, & While, 2015; Williams, 2018). Results of the HRA survey showed that the total sample of nurses averaged 1-2 vigorous workouts per week

with majority spending 0-15 minutes on each workout (See Table 2 and Figure 2). The data coincide with current research showing that although nurses spend an adequate amount of time on light exercise, they are spending less than the recommended amount of time on vigorous physical activity where heart rate and breathing is increased to keep vital organs healthy. Results of the HRA survey also highlighted how Advanced Practice Registered Nurses had higher physical activity levels than RNs and Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs). The association of education levels and exercise is also seen in populations other than nurses (Murtagh et al., 2015). APRNs may be charged with taking more of a leadership role in advocating for the health of nurses and encouraging increased physical activity levels (Waldrop, 2016). The American Holistic Nurses Association (AHNA) may wish to consider targeting their educational materials to the nurses less likely to engage in self-care, which included LVNs and RNs.

Like other studies, age was noted to be a personal factor that influenced physical activity within the nurse population (Richard & Shea, 2011; Ross et al., 2017; Williams, 2018). The HRA survey results showed that nurses 61 and older had the highest physical activity levels while nurses in the middle age group of 41-50 had the lowest physical activity levels out of all survey participants (see Table 3). The difference between these age groupings may be due to older nurses reaching retirement age and having an increased amount of time to focus on self-care. Vannucci & Weinstein (2017) suggests that middle age adults are more likely to have multiple caregiver roles, time strains, and experience burnout, which were personal factors noted to be barriers to self-care. This information coincides with the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2018) obesity prevalence rates that list the middle age population of 40-59 years old with

highest obesity rate of 42.8%. Healthcare organizations would benefit from focusing on the health of middle-aged nurses, by ensuring there is a daily focus on self-care despite multiple obligations and time constraints. Advocating for nurse self-care has been shown to increased job satisfaction and optimal patient outcomes (Blum, 2014; Ross et al., 2017).

It is interesting to note the influence of ethnicity on physical activity levels of nurses (see Table 1 and Table 4). Eighty-two percent of survey participants identified as white/Caucasian, which is slightly higher than the 80.8% white/Caucasian representation in the 2017 nursing workforce (American Association of Colleges of Nursing [AACN], 2019). Seven percent of survey participants were Black/African American and 4% were Hispanic/Latino. These statistics are also similar to the Black/African American and Hispanic/Latino communities reported by the AACN, which were 6.2% and 5.3% (AACN, 2019). HNHNTM and healthcare organizations may consider creating educational content targeting diverse populations to focus on self-care and specifically physical activity. Black/African Americans had the lowest physical activity levels from the HRA survey. The CDC reports Hispanics and non-Hispanic blacks having the highest obesity rates of 47% and 46.8% (CDC, 2018). African American/Black women were also found to have the most deaths from heart disease, followed by Caucasian/White women then Hispanics (CDC, 2019). Identifying approaches to increasing self-care activities within specific ethnic communities may benefit from further research.

This project confirmed earlier work that identified environmental factors affecting physical activity levels (Alexander et al., 2015; Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2018). Organizational support, work hours, workload, shift schedule, hours of sleep,

and employee relationships influenced HRA survey participants' physical activity (see Table 5). Within the sample, it is interesting to note that working night shift as well as sleep hours did not have strong correlations to physical activity levels. Poor physical/mental health as well as pain seemed to be the major barriers in preventing nurses from engaging in physical activity. High stress and physical demands from the job can take both a mental and physical toll on nurses. However, lack of nurse physical activity can lead to health conditions that increase the incidence of pain and emotional distress (Ross et al., 2017), which may be the cause of a continuous cycle that can diminish the health of nurses. To help end this cycle, research suggests that nurses participate in mindfulness activities like meditation and yoga to gain emotional and physical resiliency, which can increase nurse motivation to exercise (Alexander et al., 2015; Blum, 2014; Willgens & Hummel, 2016). These practices can be initiated and sustained with continuous wellness training, which was an environmental factor that showed a significant correlation to physical activity (see Table 5). Emotional support showed the strongest correlation to increased physical activity levels. Emotional support can also be obtained through wellness training as well as health coaching, which was mentioned in the literature review as an evidence-based method to enhance self-care.

Development of Educational Materials

Based on the results determined from the secondary data analysis as well as the literature review, a gap analysis was completed with the AHNA to identify educational materials to support the HNHNTM Initiative. The current educational content regarding self-care and physical activity on the AHNA website (ahna.org) is found within the resources section. Continuing Nurse Education (CNE) material are also available within

the webinar section of AHNA website, however, there are no current available webinars involving self-care activities specific to enhancing physical activity. The resources section on the AHNA website contains several webpages related to self-care that include a webpage on holistic self-care (AHNA, 2018b) as well as a webpage on stress management (AHNA, 2018c).

The webpage on holistic self-care briefly mentions exercise as a modality of self-care, however, it does not contain information on how to initiate or sustain exercise (AHNA, 2018b). In contrast, the webpage on stress management has a section dedicated to exercise as well as provides information on strategies for incorporating exercise into daily life (AHNA, 2018c). This section, however, does not offer a way to engage with nurses and to track whether nurses are able to initiate and sustain these activities. The ability to determine one's own self-efficacy as well as engaging in continuous wellness training activities were shown to enhance self-care within the literature (Blum, 2014; Khodaveisi et al., 2017; Richard & Shea, 2011). The HRA survey results also showed that wellness training and emotional support had a strong correlation to increased physical activity levels. Nurses who visit the AHNA website may benefit from educational content that allow them to engage with other nurses regarding physical activity challenges, potential exercise goals, and motivational activities.

Revision of both the holistic self-care and stress management webpages on the AHNA website is planned by the author as requested by the AHNA Executive Director to contribute to the HNHN™ initiative. Due to the confines of the DNP course schedule, the educational content revision will continue after project submission. An educational video describing this HNHN™ project and results will be added to the holistic self-care

webpage. In addition, a video that details wellness training activities that are suggested to help increase physical activity of nurses will be added to the exercise section of the stress management webpage. Accompanying the videos will be a webinar PowerPoint available to nurses for CNE credit as well as a 7-week self-care social media challenge with a prospective start date of April 27, 2020.

The author plans to engage with nurse participants on the comment sections of the videos as well as on social media platforms from April 27, 2020 to June 12, 2020 by assessing participants' weekly physical activity goals and providing motivation through informational online discussion and inspirational social media posts to achieve those goals. Physical activity goals of challenge participants will be assessed utilizing SurveyMonkey. The challenge will be evaluated by recording the number of participants that respond to the online survey as well as their responses regarding physical activity goals that were completed within the specified time frame.

With the physical activity challenge as well as the new educational content, the author aims to close the gap of knowledge and skills that nurses may have regarding methods to initiate and sustain physical activity. Desired learning outcomes of educational content include: 1.) nurse participants will recognize personal and environmental factors associated with self-care behaviors specific to physical activity, and 2.) nurse participants will be able to identify how they can evaluate and improve their own self-care behaviors via the HNHNTM Initiative. The AHNA Executive Director will evaluate the educational content and appropriateness to provide CNE credits utilizing the 5 key criteria mentioned within the methods section: (a) adequate completion of the gap

analysis, (b) content development and delivery, (c) learner engagement strategies, (d) holistic philosophy, and (e) evaluation of the learning outcomes (see Appendix B).

Clinical Implications

Nurse self-care is a significant concept that may need increased attention from healthcare organizations and professionals. Focusing on nurse self-care can play a part in improving the overall effectiveness of the healthcare industry since nurses represent a major percentage of the workforce and require optimal health for indicators like job satisfaction and positive patient outcomes. Healthcare organizations as well as professional nursing organizations may benefit from providing opportunities for nurses to explore their current self-care status and work towards their future goals. Continuous education and training could also be vital to ensuring that nurses can sustain their self-care activities (e.g. physical activity).

Limitations

There are limitations to this DNP project. One limitation is that Hispanic/Latino was listed as a demographic category among other races. Hispanic/Latino should be considered an ethnicity that may include other racial categories like white/Caucasian and Black/African American. Another limitation is that survey responses from nurse participants may not be accurate because self-report has inherent limitations. Survey participants also run the risk of misinterpreting survey questions and answering based on their own understanding. In addition, unanswered questions by survey participants contributed to the limitations of this project since the missing data could have affected project outcomes.

Conclusion

This DNP project highlights barriers to nurse self-care as well as methods that may help nurses to initiate and sustain self-care behaviors specific to physical activity as a contribution to the HNHN™ Initiative. When looking at self-care domains such as physical activity, nurses were found to be healthier than the average American (ANA, 2017). This project utilized tenets of Social Cognitive Theory to explore how extrinsic factors (such as lack of support from institutions) as well as intrinsic factors (such as personal beliefs and personal attributes) can play a part in determining health outcomes for nurses. Healthcare organizations and professionals face the task of determining effective approaches to combating this issue and prioritizing self-care solutions. To improve self-care behaviors, researchers recommend assessing healthcare workers' self-efficacy in addition to providing continuous individualized educational and motivational training programs. Contributing to the HNHN™ initiative by assessing needs, relaying vital information, and creating periodic challenges can aid in engaging a diverse population of nurses while providing the motivation needed to maintain these behaviors.

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APPENDIX A

GAP ANALYSIS FOR DNP PROJECT EDUCATIONAL AIM

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GAP ANALYSIS WORKSHEET for INDIVIDUAL EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

Idea / Need for Educational Activity: What is the Root Cause	Current State of Learner	Desired State of Learner	Gap	Is Gap in Knowledge, Skills, Professional Practice, Other?	Additional Evidence Supporting Educational Need	Learning Outcome
<p>Idea: -Self-care PowerPoint presentation (PPT) Webinar -Informational self-care videos (links in PPT) -Social media challenge (detailed in PPT)</p> <p>Need/Root Cause: American Nurses Association (ANA) data indicates</p>	<p>AHNA Resources: -<u>Holistic self-care webpage</u>: no tools to maintain exercise -<u>Holistic stress management</u>: tools for exercise, no engagement on webpage</p> <p>AHNA CNE: no webinars regarding physical activity</p>	<p>-Nurses to have access to information regarding methods to initiate and sustain physical activity</p> <p>-Nurse awareness to platforms for engaging with other nurses to discuss goals and increase motivation for physical activity</p>	<p>Nurses may have adequate knowledge of self-care practices needed for optimal health; however, research shows that nurses have not been able to meet health standards for self-care.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Knowledge <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Skills <input type="checkbox"/> Professional Practice <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>	<p>Assessing efficacy and continuous wellness training activities shown to increase self-care (Blum, 2014; Khodaveisi et al., 2017; Richard & Shea, 2011). HRA survey results show that wellness training and emotional support had a strong correlation to</p>	<p>-Nurse participants will recognize at least 3 personal and 3 environmental factors associated with self-care behaviors specific to physical activity - Nurse participants will be able to identify how they can evaluate and improve their own self-care behaviors via the Healthy</p>

nurses unhealthier than average American					increased physical activity levels.	Nurse Healthy Nation™ Initiative
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APPENDIX B

AHNA EDUCATIONAL DESIGN CRITERIA SAMPLE

Professional Practice Gap / Needs Assessment (AHNA Application IV Section A.1.)

The process of planning begins with identifying when CNE or IPCE might be a desired intervention to address a change in a standard of care, a problem that exists in practice or an opportunity to advance nursing practice.

The Nurse Planner and Planning Committee starts by analyzing data that validate the need for the educational activity. This analysis forms the basis of identifying the professional practice gap.

- IV.A.1.a. What is the learner's *current state* – responses must be limited to what is the question, problem, or opportunity for change and growth? This is not a description of the course.
- IV.A.1.b. What is the *desired state* – what should the nurse/learner know (knowledge), know how to do (skill), or practice differently in order to move the practice of nursing forward?
- IV.A.1.c. The *professional practice gap* can then be defined by the difference between the current state and the desired state of practice. The NP must document where this gap exists in terms of knowledge, skills and/or practice.

It is important to note that a professional practice gap may exist for Registered Nurses or healthcare teams regardless of the practice setting. Professional practice gaps are not limited to clinical practice; they may also exist in areas of professional work such as administration, education, and research.

It is important to remember that gaps in all areas are not likely to be met in a short educational activity. The Nurse Planner is mindful of this as the activity is planned; for example, the learner may first need knowledge (cognitive) before being able to perform the skill. There is no requirement that every educational activity address gaps in all areas; it is required that the educational activity be developed in order to address the identified gap.

A useful tool for developing the needs assessment is the Gap Analysis Worksheet for Individual Educational Activities (*Appendix C: Gap Analysis Worksheet for Individual Educational Activities*)

Evidence to Validate Practice Gap (AHNA Application IV Section A.2)

Identify sources of evidence as well as a brief description of how these resources validate the current state and the gap(s).

Target Audience (AHNA Application IV Section A.3)

Once the educational need/gap has been identified, the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee can determine the target audience for the educational activity. The target audience is defined as the specific registered nurse learners or healthcare team members the educational activity is intended to impact.

Learning Outcome(s) (AHNA Application IV Section A.4)

The Nurse Planner and Planning Committee then develop the desired learning outcome for participants in the target audience. A learning outcome is written as a statement that reflects what the learner will be able to do as a result of participating in the educational activity. The learning outcome must be observable and measurable. It addresses the educational needs (knowledge, skills, and/or practices) that contribute to the professional practice gap, and achieving the learning

outcome results in narrowing or closing the gap. A learning outcome may be assessed short term or long term. There may be more than one learning outcome for an educational activity (e.g. conferences with different learning tracks).

As a point of clarification, it is essential to differentiate learning objectives from the learning outcomes. Learning objectives define the expected goal of a presentation, course or curriculum in terms of demonstrable skills or knowledge that will be acquired as a result of instruction; they tend to be specific and discrete units of knowledge (e.g. 'Define holistic nursing', 'Identify three aspects of presence'). Learning outcomes are statements that identify a broad change in nursing practice made up of many units of knowledge. They describe measurable and essential mastered content, knowledge, reflecting skills and competencies resulting from the educational activity (e.g. 'The learner will address the spiritual needs of their patients', 'The learner will apply principles of holism in developing nursing curriculum).

Content Development and Delivery (AHNA Application IV Section B)

Content for the educational activity may be chosen by the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee, or it may be selected by others participating in the educational activity such as individual speakers or authors. It is the responsibility of the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee to ensure that content is based on the most current evidence, which may include, but is not limited to, evidence-based practice, literature, peer-reviewed journals, clinical guidelines, best practices, and content experts' opinion. If there is concern that content selected is not based on best available evidence or may be biased within the educational activity, the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee may choose to engage a Content Reviewer. The purpose of a Content Reviewer is to provide independent and expert evaluation of content to ensure best available evidence is presented, content is balanced, and content is not promotional or biased. The Content Reviewer is **not** a member of the Planning Committee.

In a Blended Educational Activity, the NP must describe how the out-of-class activities inform the educational content in order to address the professional practice gap. The entirety of the educational activity must be cohesive.

References and resources must be clearly identified (AHNA Application IV Section B.1.a). If, for example, a website is cited, the Nurse Planner must specify what exactly on this site is relevant to the educational activity. The Nurse Planner must be discerning when reviewing references; while 5 – 7 years is a helpful guide; some historical texts are relevant. On the other hand, some areas are changing so rapidly that 5-year-old reference materials may be outdated.

Learner Engagement Strategies (AHNA Application IV Section B.2)

As part of the design process, the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee develop ways to actively engage learners in the educational activity. Strategies to engage learners may include, but are not limited to, integrating opportunities for dialogue or question/answer, including time for self-check or reflection, analyzing case studies, and providing opportunities for problem-based learning. Active learner engagement may function as an opportunity for formative assessment during the educational activity by providing the presenter with immediate learner feedback. In congruence with ANCC criteria and holistic philosophy “Lecture & PowerPoint” are not sufficient as the sole teaching strategies.

Holistic Philosophy (AHNA Application IV Section B.3)

As part of the design process, the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee must describe how the philosophy of holism is foundational to and integrated within the educational activity. This may include relating the content to the AHNA Core Values and/or the AHNA/ANA *Holistic Nursing: Scope & Standards of Practice* (2013).

Evaluation of the Learning Outcomes (AHNA Application Section V)

The evaluation process is the means by which the NP and the Planning Committee determine to what extent the learning outcome has been met. The evaluation components and method(s) of evaluation should be relative to the identified gaps and the desired learning outcome(s) of the educational activity. This assessment may be *formative* and integrated within the educational activity and/or *summative* at the conclusion of the educational activity. Evaluation methods include assessment of change in knowledge, skills, and/or practice of the target audience. Change in knowledge, skills, and/or practice may or may not occur based on a variety of factors; however, evaluation should assess for such change. Evaluation may also include collecting data that reflects barriers to learner change.

See possible short and long-term evaluation methods to assess change in practice listed in the AHNA Application Section V.

Following the conclusion of the educational activity, the Nurse Planner and Planning Committee review the evaluation data to assess the impact of the educational activity and determine how results may be used to guide future updates to the content or the development of other educational activities, as applicable.